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SPATIAL PATTERN OF HOUSING IN NEWLY EMERGED VILLAGE AFTER DESERTION.

Vikram Agone¹ and S.M.Bhamare²

Abstract

This paper attempts a spatial analysis of house types and pattern of newly emerged rural settlement Kusumba after desertion. The present settlement follows checker board pattern like Dhule city in Maharashtra adopted by Sir Vishweshariya and further followed by Chandigarh a Central Territory of India. The streets are oriented towards the national highway (NH 6) and district highway. The housing typology has been attempted on the basis of size of the house, ratio between population and size of house, occupation, per capita income of the house. On these bases it is found that 79 % of the houses are medium sized with big family size. Occupation of 82 % house dwellers is farming with low per capita income. The remaining very low percent of houses are either in small size with low income group, high family size and discrete non agricultural occupations or big size house with high income group low family size and occupation services as well as trade, transport business and agriculture. The 90% of the houses on the national highway engaged in, hotels, spare part, repairing, puncture and trade and transport business. The last street (Street no7) away from the national highway is reserved for earthen pot makers, carpenters and welders. Though the village is well planned after desertion nearly 80% houses are medium sized with low income group and farming occupations.

Key words: Housing Pattern, Remote Sensing, GIS, Desertion.

Introduction:-

More than seventy percent of population of India is rural residential. There are nearly 5.76 lakh rural settlements of different sizes. Some of the settlements especially newly rehabilitated settlements after desertion are well planned. The planned rural settlements are a sort of natural growth in their physical and cultural setting with a characteristic spatial pattern of house types. The spatial analysis of rural house type and pattern provides significant information of social, cultural, political and economic status of the residential rural India. The residential area of newly well planned after desertion of village comprises the system of housing units, roads streets, lane by lane, income, occupational structures, drainage networks, civic amenities, communications etc. The house types and pattern differs from village to village and city to city (Boyce 1971). The difference in house types and patterns may be ascribed to the various factors like site, situations, historical events, political, social cultural, economic, environmental and natural calamities. The interaction of these factors produce typical house type pattern of the settlements. In view of this the present paper aims to analyze house types and pattern of Kusumba village in Dhule Tahasil and District in Maharashtra state.

Objectives:

The main objectives are:

1. To understand site, situation and history of Kusumba village settlement
2. To examine type, size, dwellers per house carpet area, occupation and income.
2. To attempt the classification of house type on the basis of size dwellers, occupation and income in order to understand the status and spatial pattern of house types.

Data Source and Methodology:

The population data is obtained from the government publication of district statistical handbook and census. The spatial data of houses and village is obtained from Geoeye satellite imageries and partially from GPS field survey. The housing typology has been attempted on the basis of size of the house, ratio between population and size of house, occupation, per capita income of the house. The size of the house is determined on the basis of carpet area. The house wise population density estimated by taking ratio of house dwellers to carpet area of house. The house wise occupation and income is obtained in field survey for estimation per capita house income. The parameter wise percentage is grouped into three categories high, medium and low classification. The results are discussed in order to obtain interpretative research potentials.

Site, Situation and History of Village Kusumba.

Kusumba Village is name derived from the union of two local words Kusum + Amba. Kusum means the flower from which colour is derived and Mango trees. Before desertion of former village it was known for colour makers (Rangaris) and mango fruits. The former settlement of rangaris was on concave bank of river Panzara. It was destroyed by alluvial flood (catastrophic flood.) in 1872 and shifted at a safe distance nearly 1.5 kms south of present channel of river Panzara. At present village extent between lat $20.54^{\circ}44.6''\text{N}$ and $20.55^{\circ}27.3''\text{N}$ and long $74.35^{\circ}47.2''\text{E}$ and $74.36^{\circ}1.8''\text{E}$. The east-west extension of the village is confined by Gavnila stream to the east and Hirasana nala to west. The new village is criss-crossed by Asian highway no 46 and State Highway No 10. The significance of village is as a weekly rural market center. The basic amenities and facilities available are primary school(4), high school with junior college (2), degree college(1), Deaf and Dumb school(1), Aashramshala(1), Balwadies/Anganwadies(4), Primary Health Center, Branch of D.D.C.C. And State bank of India And one Co-operative Credit Society. The total population of village is 13000 as per Census 2011. Most of the population is engaged in farming occupation. Therefore the main function of the village is agriculture. However at least one person from 75% is working as a primary teacher as well as V.D.O.

Location Map

Figure 1 Location Map of Kusumba Village

Figure 2 Kusumba village present location

Figure 3 Kusumba Village checkerboard settlement pattern

Results and Discussions:

The housing typology has been attempted on the basis of size of the house, ratio between population and size of house (Population per House), occupation and per capita income of the house. (Table No.1) The housing types follows checker board pattern. Each house row types with nearly similar types and their number in each row ranges between 50 and 55.

Table 1 Details of Housing Type criteria

Criteria	House Type	Size	Share %
Size of House	i) Small houses	< 55 x 30 feet medium house	11
	ii) Medium house	60 X 32 feet.	79
	iii) Big house.	>65 X 34 feet including	9
	iv) Biggest house	double storey houses Wada	< 1
Occupations	i) Farming.& dairying		82
	ii) Service		11
	iii) Business		07
Per capita income of House	i) low income group	< Rs.8000/-	21
	ii) medium income group	Rs.8000-24000/-	63
	iii) High income group.	>Rs.24000/-	16

Housing Typology on the Size of House:

The size of the house is determined on the basis of carpet area of the house which is divided into four compartments the big compartment along axial length of the house is the leaving room. A comparatively small compartment behind the living is a store house. Veranda lies in front of living room with open access towards lane. The kitchen is behind the store room in small compartment. It is almost open in back side of the house. Open bathroom and water well are in opposites corners behind the kitchen.

The houses size dimensions are 60 feet x 32 feet on an average. This house is considered as a medium. The house size greater than medium size is treated as big house. Some of the big houses are double storey. The biggest house is known as Wada. There is only one Wada of landlord in Kusumba village in the center of the village. The size of small house is less than medium house.

The housing types on the basis of size have been classified into four groups (table.1) The small houses in Kusumba village are 11%. These are essentially earthen build houses with flat room made up of wooden grill covered by thatch and earthen material. Such houses are essentially found in low rainfall area.

The medium houses occupy highest percentages (79 %) of the total. These houses are better than small houses and covers extra amenities. The house is attached with separate closed kitchen and bathroom. They are two categories in medium size houses. Some are made up of bricks and concretes slabs attached with separate toilet bathroom, kitchen, devghar along with living and store rooms. The agriculture is the main occupation of this house, but least one member of this house is in service like primary teacher, VDO, Gram sevak, secretary in multipurpose society etc.

The big size house is essentially two storey house. It has amenities like urban house types. These houses are either of landlords or better service man house like secondary and college teachers, businessman's houses. Such houses account 9% Of the total houses in Kusumba. There is only one biggest house in the form of fortified walls from all sides known as Wada. One member from this Wada was well educated in law (Barrister at law of London) and served in High court Mumbai. He is not alive but his sons and grandsons are in good services like engineers, doctors in big cities. This is a united family till living 24 members at present. They all are related to faming activities.

Population per house:

The population per house is estimated on the basis of the dwellers in the houses. The number of dwellers in each house varies greatly. In some of the big houses they are only two and some of small houses they are eight in numbers. In Wada they are 24 in numbers.

Occupation:

The main occupation of Kusumba village is farming and dairying and occupies 82% of the houses in Kusumba. Eleven percentages houses are engaged in service and remaining 07 % in business.

Per Capita Income of houses:

On the basis of income house types of the Kusumba village may be classified into three groups. viz low income group houses, medium income group house group and high income group houses, It is found that 63% houses are medium income groups . Their main occupation is farming. 21 % houses are low income group houses. They all are engaged agricultural workers activities. The remaining very low percent of houses are either in small size with low income group, high family size and discrete non agricultural occupations or big size house with high income group low family size and occupation services as well as trade, transport business and agriculture. The 90% of the houses on the national highway engaged in, hotels, spare part, repairing, puncture and trade and transport business. The last street (Street no7) away from the national highway is reserved for earthen pot makers, carpenters and welders. Though the village is well planned after desertion nearly 80% houses are medium sized with low income group and farming occupations.

Conclusion:

The planned rural settlements are a sort of natural growth in their physical and cultural setting with a characteristic spatial pattern of house types. The spatial analysis of rural house type and pattern provides significant information of social, cultural, political and economic status of the residential rural India. The residential area of newly well planned after desertion of village comprises the system of housing units, roads streets, lane by lane, income, occupational structures, drainage networks, civic amenities, communications etc. The farming activity plays key role in rural house types though it is new well planned after desertion. From the present study it is found that 79 % of the houses are medium sized with big family size. Occupation of 82 % house dwellers is farming with low per capita income. The remaining very low percent of houses are either in small size with low income group, high family size and discrete non agricultural occupations or big size house with high income group low family size and occupation services as well as trade, transport business and agriculture. The 90% of the houses on the national highway engaged in, hotels, spare part, repairing, puncture and trade and transport business. The last street (Street no7) away from the national highway is reserved for earthen pot makers, carpenters and welders. Though the village is well planned after desertion nearly 80% houses are medium sized with low income group and farming occupations.

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